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USE OF LITERARY MATERIALS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

The importance of integrating literature into second language learning programs has been discussed for years, and literature has begun to return into language classes in recent years at an increasing rate. In fact, literature was included into language teaching from the very beginning when modern languages began to appear in the curriculum of schools in Europe in the 18 th century .Grammar Translation Method was the first method of teaching foreign languages ; and this method was used for the longest period of time. In the history of language teaching from the beginning until early 20th century The aim of this method was “ to learn a language in order to its literature in order to benefit from the mental discipline and intellectual development that result from foreign language study”. The beginning of the 20th century witnessed efforts to “emancipate modern language from grammar\translation pedagogy”.

KEYWORDS: *Writing Skills, Instructions, Grammatical Correctness, Texts, Errors, Cognitive Challenges*

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